

MANUAL HANDLING AND CARRYING A TURKEY

BEFORE CATCHING

Dim the lights to keep the birds calm.

Avoid loud noises.

All movements must be **slow** and **steady**.

Wear **dark** coloured clothing.

HOW TO MANUALLY CATCH TURKEYS

For small or young turkeys ($\leq 1\text{kg}$)

1 Place one hand on each side of the body, over the wings, with the legs hanging free.

Due to the strength of turkeys, the stockperson should take **secure hold around both legs** with one hand.

2 Gently shift the bird so that the breast is in the palm of one hand.

For turkeys above 1kg

1 From behind, grasp with one hand by the two legs.

2 Gently lower the turkey onto its breast.

3 Grasp the shoulder of the wing furthest away to lift and carry the bird close to the body.

Turkeys (above 5kg) can also be directly grasped by the base of one wing with one hand and the contralateral shank with the other, lifted and carried close to the stockpersons body.

FOR CRATING

1 Grasp the base of the wings and the contralateral leg (or both legs).

2 Push into the crate sliding the keel bone on the floor of the crate with the bird's head facing forward.

PLACEMENT INTO A CONE FOR EUTHANASIA

For small or young turkeys

2 Firmly clench the legs between your outstretched fingers.

3 The wings can be controlled by the opposite hand or by holding the bird against the body, under your arm.

For turkeys above 1kg

To avoid having to lift **heavy turkeys** for stunning, they may be manually restrained on the ground by doing **step 2**.

WHAT ARE THE OPTIMUM TURKEY RESTRAINT DEVICES ?

The use of restraint devices allows that only **one stockperson is enough** to carry out the restraining and killing. These methods allow to **calm birds** and **reduce the risk of accidental injury** (for both the bird and stockperson) during killing.

USING A CONE

Ensure that the cone is the right size for the bird.

Reduce restraint time as much as possible by being ready to stun/kill the bird immediately.

Maintain hand contact with the bird head to reduce stress.

USING A PLASTIC BIN

(alternatively)

Ensure that the bin is the right size for the bird.

Previously cut a piece the **right size** to avoid causing injury to the neck.

The turkey should be placed on the floor in a sternal recumbent position with its keel on a solid and flat surface.

For any questions or suggestions regarding this document, please contact

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